

Figure 1. Average and standard deviation of (A) total carbon (TC in mg/L), (B) total nitrogen (TN in mg/L), (C) total phosphorus (TP in $\mu\text{g/L}$); (D, E, F) β -glucosidase (Glu in $\mu\text{M MUF/mL h}$), leucine aminopeptidase (Leu in $\mu\text{M AMC/mL h}$) and Phosphatase (Pho in $\mu\text{M MUF/ mL h}$) in water; and (G, H, I) β -glucosidase (Glu in $\mu\text{M MUF/cm}^2 \text{ h}$), Leucine aminopeptidase (Leu in $\mu\text{M AMC/cm}^2 \text{ h}$) and Phosphatase in biofilm (Pho in $\mu\text{M MUF/cm}^2 \text{ h}$), respectively. Cool temperature ($T^\circ\text{C} - 18^\circ\text{C}$) in solid pattern and warm temperatures ($\Delta T^\circ\text{C} - 26^\circ\text{C}$) dashed pattern. Control treatment in green, AgNP in purple, Ag_2S in orange and AgNO_3 in grey. Two-way ANOVA and post hoc (Tukey $p < 0.05$) results are added.

Figure 2. Average and standard deviation of (A) silver accumulated in biofilm (Ag acc.), (B) biofilm biomass (mg dry weight), (C) extracellular polysaccharide substances (EPS), (D) respiration rate (Raz/Rru), (E) algal biomass, and (F) photosynthetic activity (Φ'_M) over time expressed in relative fluorescence units (rfu). Cool temperature ($T^{\circ}C - 18^{\circ}C$) in solid pattern and warm temperatures ($\Delta T^{\circ}C - 26^{\circ}C$) dashed pattern. Control in green, AgNP in purple, Ag_2S in orange and $AgNO_3$ in grey. Two-way ANOVA and post hoc (Tukey $p < 0.05$) results are added.

Figure 3. Principle component biplots of (A) physicochemical parameters – pH, calcium and magnesium (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}), oxygen (Oxy), conductivity (Cond), total carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus (TC, TN, TP), total silver in water (Ag_W) – and (B) biological parameters - biofilm biomass (dry weight, DW), silver accumulated in biofilm (Ag_Bio), extracellular polysaccharide matrix (EPS), β -glucosidase (Glu), Phosphatase (Pho) and Leucine aminopeptidase (Leu) in water (W) and in biofilm (Bio), algal biomass (F biomass) and optimal photosynthetic activity (Photosynthesis) – of each treatment throughout the experiment. Parameters were analysed under cool (T , solid pattern) and warm temperatures (ΔT , transparent pattern) for control flumes (in blue) and each silver treatment (AgNP in purple, Ag_2SNP in orange and AgNO_3 in green) at different periods, acute (circles) and chronic (triangles).

Figure 4. From bottom upwards, a schematic summary of the significant effects of temperature, silver toxicity (AgNP, Ag₂S, and Ag⁺) and their combination (T°C+ENP) on freshwater biofilms (in green) and on water physicochemistry (in blue) at different temporal scales, from 1 and 3 days (acute) to 15 and 30 days (chronic).

Variables are: total Ag concentration in water (Ag_{Total}), silver dissolved in water (Ag⁺), silver accumulated in biofilms (Ag_{acc.} in biofilm), extracellular polysaccharide substances (EPS), total carbon (TC), total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP), β-glucosidase in water (Glu_W) and in biofilm (Glu_{BIO}), leucine aminopeptidase in water (Leu_W) and in biofilm (Leu_{BIO}), and Phosphatase in water (Pho_W) and in biofilm (Pho_{BIO}) and optimal photosynthesis (photosynthesis).

Table 1. Factorial design whereby two different temperatures (18 °C and 25 °C) were combined with different silver treatments (AgNP, Ag₂SNP and AgNO₃).

	Without Ag	With Ag (<i>stressor A</i>)
Cool temperature	<i>Control</i>	Ag, Ag ₂ S, AgNO ₃
Warm temperature (<i>stressor B</i>)	ΔT	ΔTAg, ΔTAg ₂ S, ΔTAgNO ₃

Table 2. For each parameter measured, the type of interaction is determined from the individual effects of each stressor - stress of silver (AgNP, Ag₂SNP and AgNO₃) and temperature compared to control -, which are summed to determine their respective interactive effect (Di) with 95% confidence intervals. Interactions are additive (add) if the combined effects are equal to the sum of the two individual stress effect, synergistic (*syn*) if the combined effect exceeds the sum of the two individual stressors, or antagonistic (*ant*) is the combined effects is less than the sum of the individual effects. Parameters are in bold if there is a non-additive interaction under at least one of the conditions tested.

		Interaction type		
Parameter		<i>AgNP+T°C</i>	<i>Ag₂SNP+T°C</i>	<i>AgNO₃+T°C</i>
Physicochemical	Conductivity	add	add	Add
	Oxygen	add	add	Add
	pH	add	add	Add
	TC	add	add	Add
	TN	add	add	Add
	TP	<i>syn</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>Ant</i>
	Mg ²⁺	add	add	Add
	Ca ²⁺	add	add	Add
	NP Size	<i>syn</i>	<i>ant</i>	<i>Ant</i>
	Z potential	add	add	<i>Syn</i>
	Ag ⁺	add	add	add
	Total Ag	<i>syn</i>	add	add
	Biological	Biofilm biomass	<i>syn</i>	<i>syn</i>
Ag accumulated		<i>ant</i>	<i>ant</i>	<i>ant</i>
Respiration		add	add	add
Glu in water		add	<i>ant</i>	add
Glu in biofilm		add	add	add
Leu in water		add	add	add
Leu in biofilm		add	add	add
Pho in water		<i>syn</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>ant</i>
Pho in biofilm		<i>ant</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>syn</i>
Algal biomass		<i>syn</i>	<i>ant</i>	<i>ant</i>
Photosynthetic activity	<i>syn</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>syn</i>	
EPS	add	add	add	

Supplementary information

SI Figure 1. (A) a photo and (B) a schematic representation of the mesocosms set-up used to perform the experiments. (C) Detail of an individual flume dimensions.

SI Figure 2. TEM images of Ag NPs before (A & B) and after (C & D) aging in a mixture solution of 1 mM Na₂S and 10 mM NaNO₃, and size distribution (E & F) of Ag NPs after aging.

The aging (sulfidization) of AgNPs was carried out following the previously reported protocol (Kim et al. 2010). 400 mL Ag NPs suspension was poured into 500 mL mixture solution of 1 mM Na₂S and 10 mM NaNO₃ under vigorous stirring at room temperature. The NPs was isolated by centrifugation at 7000 g for one hour, after stirring at room temperature for 24 hours. Aged Ag NPs were kept in 50 mL H₂O for further characterization. TEM images of crude PVP-AgNPs provided by Amepox showed a wide size distribution (Fig. S2A and S2B). TEM results indicated two kinds of particles. Ag NPs appear to be darker in contrast but smaller in size, whereas impurities are larger in size but lighter in contrast. There is no obvious difference in contrast observed on TEM images for aged Ag NPs (Fig. S2C and S2D), indicating that impurities were washed off after centrifugation. However, some of Ag NPs became linked to each other after aging in Na₂S solution (Fig. S2C), which is also reflected by their size distribution in Fig. S2E. Particle size analysis on these aged NPs suggested that the majority of NPs are isolated with a size ca 28 nm. No particle analysis was carried out for crude Ag NPs before aging. However, the TEM images in Figure S2A and S2B showed a much smaller size than the 60 nm supplier indicated size.

SI Figure 3. High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) image and elemental mapping (Ag and S) of linked NPs (upper) and isolated NP (lower).

SI Figure 4. HRTEM Images of Ag NPs after aging in 1 mM Na₂S and 10 mM NaNO₃ for 24 hours.

To investigate the composition and structure of the aged (sulfidized) NPs, high resolution TEM and elemental mapping with Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) microanalysis were applied. Results confirmed that both linked NPs and isolated NPs are present, and that there is an Ag₂S shell formed around the initial Ag particles (Fig. S3, showing both linked particles (top row) and free particles (bottom row)). In other words, all Ag NPs are covered by Ag₂S after aging for 24 hours in Na₂S solution. This core-shell structure of Ag@Ag₂S was further supported by the existence of excess Ag. EDX indicated an Ag to S ratio of 3, higher than the ratio of 2 for Ag₂S. The majority of NPs have a core-shell structure and remained isolated after aging, implying that Ag₂S NPs formed *in situ* at the surface of the Ag NPs (Fig. S3 bottom row). If the Ag NPs stay close enough together, they would be linked by newly formed Ag₂S at the gap between them (Fig. S4a). High resolution TEM showed the atomic lattice of Ag₂S, and spacing distance of 2.46 Å was assigned for (112) planes, which is further evidence that Ag NPs were covered by Ag₂S after aging in Na₂S (Fig.4B).

SI Figure 5. Average and standard deviation of main effects of silver (DSilver in black), increase of temperature ($\Delta T^{\circ}\text{C}$ in white) and their interaction (Dinteraction in grey) for each silver form (AgNP, Ag₂SNP and AgNO₃). One-way anova followed by a post-hoc ($p < 0.05$). Letters indicate significant differences between main effects for each silver form.

SI effect size. Individual and main effects (Hedge's d values) calculations (Gurevitch et al. 2000 and Crain et al. 2008).

In this study, we combined different silver treatments (AgNP, Ag₂SNP and AgNO₃) at two different temperatures (cool and warm), leading to the experimental factorial design shown in Table S1:

Table 1	Without Ag	With Ag (stressor A)
Cool temperature	Control	Ag, Ag ₂ S or AgNO ₃
Warm temperature (stressor B)	ΔT	ΔTAg, ΔTAg ₂ S or ΔTAgNO ₃

Thus, in our study, there are two stressors - Silver - A (Ag (A1), Ag₂S (A2) and AgNO₃ (A3)) - and the increase of temperature (B). To compare expected individual effects versus observed effects, **individual effects** (the response in the presence of a stressor alone vs. the control) were calculated using the effect size (Hedge's d) Effect sizes (*d*) for each single stressor was calculated as:

$$d = \frac{m_{treat} - m_{control}}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where m_{treat} is the mean of the treatment (i.e., AgNP, Temperature) response variable, m_c is the mean value for the control. S_{pooled} is the pooled standard deviation (equation 2) where sd indicates the standard deviation of the treatment and the control. We used this simplified equation since the treatment and the control sample size are equal ($n=5$ for each sampling time and condition). Finally, $J(m)$ is a correction term for small sample bias ($n < 20$) (Hedges and Olkin 1985) (equation 3).

$$S_{pooled} = \sqrt{\frac{sd_{treat}^2 + sd_c^2}{2}} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$J(m) = 1 - \frac{3}{4n-9} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Specifically, to compare expected vs. observed results, individual effects (depicted with a lowercase d_x followed by the stressor subscript) were calculated (using Eq. 1) as

Expected mix (A+B)	vs.	Observed mix (AB)
$d_{Ag} = \frac{m_{Ag} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m) + d_{\Delta T} = \frac{m_{\Delta T} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$	vs.	$d_{\Delta TAg} = \frac{m_{\Delta TAg} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$
$d_{Ag2S} = \frac{m_{Ag2S} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m) + d_{\Delta T} = \frac{m_{\Delta T} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$	vs.	$d_{\Delta TAg2S} = \frac{m_{\Delta TAg2S} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$
$d_{AgNO3} = \frac{m_{AgNO3} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m) + d_{\Delta T} = \frac{m_{\Delta T} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$	vs.	$d_{\Delta TAgNO3} = \frac{m_{\Delta TAgNO3} - m_c}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$

To compare the net effect of a stressor (A) in the presence and absence of a second stressor (B), the **main effects** (depicted with an uppercase D , followed by the stressor subscript) of silver (D_{Ag} , D_{Ag2S} and D_{AgNO3}), and increase of temperature ($D_{\Delta T:Ag}$, $D_{\Delta T:Ag2S}$, $D_{\Delta T:AgNO3}$) and the interaction ($DI_{\Delta T:Ag}$, $DI_{\Delta T:Ag2S}$, $DI_{\Delta T:AgNO3}$) was calculated using the following equations (Crain et al. 2008):

$$D_A = \frac{(m_A + m_{AB}) - (m_B + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m) \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

$$D_B = \frac{(m_B + m_{AB}) - (m_A + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m) \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

$$D_I = \frac{(m_{AB} - m_B) - (m_A - m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m) \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

where m is the average of the stressor group indicated by the subscript and m_c is the mean value for the control as before, S_{pooled} is the pooled standard deviation (eq. 2) and $J(m)$ is the correction term from small samples bias (eq.3).

Specifically, in our study the formulas used were:

Silver forms (stressor A) (Eq. 4)	$D_{Ag} = \frac{(m_{Ag} + m_{\Delta TA_g}) - (m_{\Delta T} + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$ $D_{Ag2S} = \frac{(m_{Ag2S} + m_{\Delta TA_g2S}) - (m_{\Delta TA_g2S} + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$ $D_{AgNO3} = \frac{(m_{AgNO3} + m_{\Delta TA_gNO3}) - (m_{\Delta T} + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$
Increase of T°C (ΔT) (stressor B) (Eq. 5)	$D_{\Delta T:Ag} = \frac{(m_{\Delta T} + m_{\Delta TA_g}) - (m_{Ag} + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$ $D_{\Delta T:Ag2S} = \frac{(m_{\Delta T} + m_{\Delta TA_g2S}) - (m_{Ag2S} + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$ $D_{\Delta T:AgNO3} = \frac{(m_{\Delta T} + m_{\Delta TA_gNO3}) - (m_{AgNO3} + m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$
Interaction (Eq. 6)	$DI_{\Delta T:Ag} = \frac{(m_{\Delta TA_g} - m_{Ag}) - (m_{\Delta T} - m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$ $DI_{\Delta T:Ag2S} = \frac{(m_{\Delta TA_g2S} - m_{Ag2S}) - (m_{\Delta T} - m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$ $DI_{\Delta T:AgNO3} = \frac{(m_{\Delta TA_gNO3} - m_{AgNO3}) - (m_{\Delta T} - m_c)}{S_{pooled}} \times J(m)$

Effect size confidence intervals were calculated as:

$$95\%CI = d - t \times se_d; d + t \times se_d \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

where d is the unbiased Hedge's d , t is the t distribution with appropriate degrees of freedom ($df = N_A + N_B - 2$) and the se_d was calculated as:

$$se_d = \sqrt{\frac{n_{treat} + n_{control}}{n_{treat} \times n_{control}} + \frac{d^2}{2(n_{treat} + n_{control} - 2)}} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

Considering the direction of individual effects, we used the interaction effect size and 95% confidence interval to classify each silver and temperature combination as synergistic, antagonistic or additive (see Table S5) (Crain et al 2008). The specific criteria were as follows: (1) additive interactions (equal to the sum of single stressors) when the 95% confidence intervals overlapped zero, (2) Synergistic interactions (greater than the sum of single stressors) were specified for stressor pairs whose individual effects were either both negative or negative and positive and where the interaction effect size was less than zero ($DI < 0$) or when individual effects were both positive, interactions are interpreted in the opposite manner ($DI > 0$), and (3) antagonistic effects (less than the sum of the single stressors) when stressor pairs whose individual effects were either both negative or negative and positive and the interaction effect size was greater than zero ($DI > 0$) or

individual effects were both positive, interactions are interpreted in the opposite manner ($DI < 0$); summarised in the following table:

Non-significant	Significant					
Additive	Synergistic			Antagonistic		
$DI \geq 0 \leq DI$	-	-	$DI < 0$	-	-	$DI > 0$
	-	+	$DI < 0$	-	+	$DI > 0$
	+	+	$DI > 0$	+	+	$DI < 0$

SI Table S1. Average (avg) ± standard deviation (SD) of physicochemical variables at acute (A = 0h, 1 and 3 days) and chronic (C = 0h, 15 and 30 days) times for (i) cool (T°C) and warm temperatures (ΔT°C) (n = 60), (ii) control and silver treatments (AgNP, Ag₂SNP and AgNO₃) (n = 30), and (iii) the combination. Physicochemical variables are: conductivity in μS/cm, dissolved oxygen in mg/L, pH, total carbon concentration (TC) in mg/L, total nitrogen concentration (TN) in mg/L, total phosphorous (TP) in μg/L, magnesium (Mg⁺²) in mg/L, calcium (Ca⁺²) in mg/L, total silver and silver dissolved in water (Ag_{Total} and Ag⁺) in μg/L. Two way ANOVA results are shown indicating the F and p-values. Different letters indicate significant differences (Tukey-b test) between treatments. *ns*, means not significant and *nd*, means no data.

		Cond (μS/cm)		Oxy (mg/L)		pH		TC (mg/L)		TN (mg/L)		TP (μg/L)		Mg ⁺² (mg/L)		Ca ⁺² (mg/L)		Ag _{Total} (μg/L)		Ag ⁺ (μg/L)		
		A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	
Temperature	T°C	avg	194.93	175.28	11.02	11.04	8.94	9.02	2.86	2.84	0.16	0.18	96.82	297.82	2.98	2.50	22.44	19.13	3.67	5.73	0.17	0.21
		SD	2.66	15.08	0.91	0.77	1.05	0.82	1.69	1.39	0.07	0.10	79.97	189.73	0.81	0.48	3.67	3.09	2.88	6.18	0.13	0.18
	ΔT°C	avg	235.87	205.02	9.14	8.84	9.01	8.43	2.66	2.04	0.25	0.26	239.78	276.62	3.78	2.92	25.91	22.18	4.98	2.57	0.15	0.14
		SD	14.73	26.18	0.65	0.52	0.50	0.33	1.35	0.89	0.08	0.12	125.71	137.39	0.78	0.77	4.04	4.64	6.96	0.92	0.07	0.07
		F	511.88	51.11	179.21	362.21	<i>ns</i>	25.14	<i>ns</i>	10.14	58.48	26.27	76.62	<i>ns</i>	27.86	7.86	23.32	13.65	<i>ns</i>	28.02	<i>ns</i>	9.34
	p-value	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001		0.0001		0.005	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	<i>ns</i>	0.0001	0.01	0.0001	0.0001		0.0001	<i>ns</i>	0.005	
Silver treatment	Control	avg	215.88	192.35	10.21	10.11	9.01	8.76	2.44	2.12 ^b	0.20	0.18 _b	143.05 ^b	256.52 ^{ab}	3.40	2.68	24.44	20.33	2.36 ^b	2.36 ^b	0.12 ^b	0.12 ^b
		SD	27.32	21.85	1.49	1.57	0.14	0.70	0.45	0.62	0.05	0.05	102.51	19.00	0.69	0.18	3.11	1.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	AgNP	avg	215.70	190.93	10.11	9.98	8.98	8.72	3.36	2.92 ^a	0.23	0.26 ^a	201.95 ^b	306.81 ^{ab}	3.44	2.69	24.93	20.75	10.05 ^a	8.20 ^a	0.17 ^{ab}	0.28 ^a
		SD	29.56	21.31	1.41	1.69	0.02	0.44	0.21	0.48	0.07	0.09	142.65	13.39	0.24	0.20	0.69	1.88	3.95	7.09	0.00	0.12
	Ag ₂ SNP	avg	214.60	188.37	10.24	9.92	9.09	8.74	2.60	2.59 ^{ab}	0.20	0.21 ^{ab}	69.50 ^c	255.94 ^b	3.27	2.84	23.79	21.36	2.36 ^b	2.36 ^b	0.12 ^b	0.12 ^b
		SD	30.83	20.41	1.09	1.40	0.29	0.17	0.18	0.61	0.04	0.05	62.15	17.66	0.73	0.43	3.43	2.98	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	AgNO ₃	avg	215.42	188.95	9.75	9.75	8.83	8.68	2.62	2.14 ^b	0.21	0.25 ^{ab}	258.70 ^a	329.59 ^a	3.41	2.64	23.55	20.19	2.54 ^b	3.68 ^b	0.21 ^a	0.17 ^b
	SD	28.07	20.53	1.32	1.57	0.05	0.37	0.15	0.56	0.08	0.03	97.04	47.91	0.61	0.39	2.60	2.02	0.25	1.87	0.05	0.07	
	F	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	3.62	<i>ns</i>	3.77	33.579	2.54	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	43.889	20.55	6.471	12.83	
	p-value								0.05		0.05	0.0001	0.05					0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	
T°C * Treatment		<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>yes</i>	<i>ns</i>	<i>yes</i>	
F																			11.6		3.18	
p-value																			0.0001		0.05	

SI Table S2. Average (avg) ± standard deviation (SD) of biological variables at acute (A = 0h, 1 and 3 days) and chronic (C = 0h, 15 and 30 days) times for (i) cool (T°C) and warm temperatures (ΔT°C) (n = 60), (ii) control and silver treatments (AgNP, Ag₂SNP and AgNO₃) (n = 30), and (iii) the combination. Biological variables are: biofilm biomass (dry weight, DW) in mg/L, silver accumulated in biofilm (Ag_{acc}) in μg/g DW, respiration (resp) as a Raz/Rrz ratio, extracellular polysaccharide matrix (EPS) as μL of total carbohydrates /μL Biofilm, β-glucosidase (Glu) and Phosphatase (Pho) in water and biofilm as μM of MUF/mL and μM of MUF/cm², respectively, and Leucine aminopeptidase (Leu) in water and in biofilm as μM of AMC/mL and μM of AMC/cm², respectively, and finally algal biomass (F₀) and optimal photosynthetic activity (Φ_M). Two-way ANOVA results are shown indicating the F and p-values. Different letters (a, b, c) indicate significant differences (Tukey-b test) between treatments. *ns*, means not significant and *nd*, means no data.

			DW mg/L		Ag acc. μg/g DW		Resp		EPS μL carbohydrates /μL Biofilm		Glu in water μM MUF/mL h		Glu in biofilm μM MUF/cm ² h		Leu in water μM AMC-Leu/mL		Leu in biofilm μM AMC/cm ² h		Pho in water μM MUF/mL h		Pho in biofilm μM MUF/cm ² h		F ₀		Φ _M														
			A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C	A	C													
Temperature	T°C	avg	23.26	29.49	33.57	51.68	nd	0.010	0.32	0.31	25.94	26.82	1.37	1.19	30.88	28.29	2.45	2.21	11.39	87.86	8.04	10.25	89.41	88.38	0.24	0.30													
		SD	14.87	30.49	35.17	49.15	nd	0.003	0.09	0.10	2.32	2.33	0.37	0.52	2.65	2.90	0.79	0.99	1.21	55.35	3.41	2.88	43.32	50.89	0.11	0.16													
	ΔT°C	avg	56.84	34.67	21.63	97.35	nd	0.013	0.34	0.32	28.56	25.99	1.23	1.16	44.25	46.09	1.31	1.91	1317.58	845.58	73.34	82.61	108.29	115.81	0.41	0.38													
		SD	58.93	44.29	31.33	186.88	nd	0.003	0.12	0.12	2.70	2.76	0.21	0.22	13.65	12.37	0.23	0.89	198.31	576.11	17.13	18.57	76.03	116.68	0.26	0.35													
	F		15.60		19.16		ns	20.75			33.86		ns		3.946		ns		58.688		157.87		ns		160.617		ns	70.30		51.19		1404.502		1717.54		ns		16.355	
p-value		0.0001		0.0001		ns	0.0001			ns		ns		0.0001		ns		0.0001		0.0001		ns		ns		0.0001		0.0001		0.0001		0.0001		0.0001		0.0001			
Silver treatment	Control	avg	36.76	29.12	11.7 ^b	11.89 ^b	nd	0.013 ^b	0.32 ^{bc}	0.31 ^b	27.74	26.88 ^{ab}	1.36	1.37 ^a	38.13	38.01	1.90	2.09	683.18	462.91	40.59	47.75 ^{ab}	103.79 ^{ab}	102.63	0.33	0.32													
		SD	16.12	13.76	4.68	6.84	nd	0.004	0.13	0.13	2.83	0.05	0.13	0.15	10.50	12.69	0.78	0.17	949.59	533.43	46.72	53.36	14.23	15.48	0.14	0.04													
	AgNP	avg	47.90	40.80	48.2 ^a	179.64 ^a	nd	0.010 ^a	0.41 ^a	0.39 ^a	27.71	27.40 ^a	1.31	1.23 ^{ab}	38.14	37.82	1.86	2.14	675.54	464.95	41.22	46.28 ^{ab}	114.66 ^a	130.27	0.37	0.43													
		SD	34.42	6.84	15.30	130.21	nd	0.002	0.02	0.05	3.19	0.15	0.07	0.04	9.08	12.54	0.77	0.07	939.59	529.87	46.36	49.97	18.59	27.50	0.13	0.08													
	Ag ₂ SNP	avg	44.43	32.58	21.69 ^b	31.90 ^b	nd	0.012 ^b	0.35 ^{ab}	0.34 ^{ab}	26.73	25.81 ^{ab}	1.28	1.09 ^{bc}	36.89	35.91	1.87	2.09	648.24	478.87	41.18	50.71 ^a	103.01 ^{ab}	102.65	0.34	0.34													
		SD	29.74	13.20	17.83	6.43	nd	0.004	0.01	0.02	0.74	1.94	0.11	0.00	9.31	12.30	0.86	0.25	900.62	555.28	45.87	56.45	8.52	29.75	0.09	0.10													
	AgNO ₃	avg	31.10	25.83	28.75 ^b	74.62 ^a	nd	0.011 ^a	0.23 ^c	0.23 ^c	26.81	25.52 ^b	1.24	1.01 ^c	37.09	37.03	1.89	1.93	650.99	460.15	39.77	40.98 ^b	73.95 ^b	72.82	0.27	0.26													
SD		14.69	5.49	26.57	12.24	nd	0.002	0.06	0.08	2.13	0.22	0.07	0.03	8.93	12.81	0.81	0.37	904.66	524.59	45.76	44.90	12.06	4.86	0.11	0.00														
F		ns	ns	13.612	25.81	ns	8.68	15.62	24.22	ns	4.09	ns	6.29	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	2.73	2.778	ns	ns	ns	ns												
p-value		ns	ns	0.0001	0.0001	ns	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	ns	0.01	ns	0.001	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.05	0.05	ns	ns	ns	ns												
T°C * Treatment			ns	ns	yes	ns	ns	yes	yes	yes	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns													
F					2.923			3.34	6.81	23.77																													
p-value					0.05			0.05	0.0001	0.0001																													

SI Table S3. Complementary information of Figure 5. Main effect ANOVA results (F and p values) from silver stressor ($D_{Ag} - D_{Ag2S} - D_{AgNO3}$), temperature ($D_{\Delta T:Ag} - D_{\Delta T:Ag2S} - D_{\Delta T:AgNO3}$) and their interaction ($DI_{\Delta T:Ag} - DI_{\Delta T:Ag2S} - DI_{\Delta T:AgNO3}$) (N = 5, main effect of each sampling time). *ns* means no significant.

Parameters	$D_{Ag} - D_{\Delta T:Ag} - DI_{\Delta T:Ag}$	$D_{Ag2S} - D_{\Delta T:Ag2S} - DI_{\Delta T:Ag2S}$	$D_{AgNO3} - D_{\Delta T:AgNO3} - DI_{\Delta T:AgNO3}$
Conductivity	ns	F = 3.83, p < 0.05	F = 9.02, p < 0.005
Oxy	F = 646.06, p < 0.001	F = 551.23, p < 0.000	F = 18.14, p < 0.000
pH	F = 257.76, p < 0.001	F = 304.24, p < 0.000	F = 17.36, p < 0.000
TC	F = 23.91, p < 0.001	F = 16.05, p < 0.000	F = 11.54, p < 0.005
TN	F = 49.25, p < 0.001	F = 61.93, p < 0.000	F = 11.45, p < 0.005
TP	ns	ns	ns
Mg²⁺	F = 63.94, p < 0.001	F = 120.32, p < 0.000	F = 14.07, p < 0.001
Ca²⁺	ns	ns	F = 4.78, p < 0.05
S_{nm}	F = 6.27, p < 0.05	ns	ns
Z_{mV}	F = 10.54, p < 0.005	ns	F = 6.84, p < 0.01
Ag⁺	F = 13.26, p < 0.001	ns	F = 8.39, p < 0.005
Total Ag	ns	ns	ns
Biofilm biomass	ns	ns	ns
Ag_{acc}	ns	ns	ns
Respiration	ns	ns	ns
Glu_W	F = 9.89, p < 0.005	ns	ns
Glu_{Bio}	F = 100.14, p < 0.001	F = 53.46, p < 0.000	F = 9.38, p < 0.005
Leu_W	F = 4.58, p < 0.001	F = 3.95, p < 0.048	ns
Leu_{Bio}	F = 13.86, p < 0.005	F = 12.30, p < 0.001	F = 9.18, p < 0.005
Pho_W	F = 6.91, p < 0.05	F = 8.08, p < 0.006	F = 4.32, p < 0.05
Pho_{Bio}	F = 18.54, p < 0.001	F = 79.70, p < 0.000	F = 33.06, p < 0.000
Algal biomass (Fo)	F = 5.43, p < 0.05	F = 5.56, p < 0.020	F = 5.33, p < 0.05
Φ_M	F = 4.56, p < 0.05	F = 5.64, p < 0.019	F = 3.92, p < 0.05
EPS	F = 158.63, p < 0.001	F = 126.09, p < 0.000	F = 13.67, p < 0.001

Table SI 4. List of parameters used for analyses of cumulative effect of stressor pairs. Listed is individual effect of each stressor (Stressor A and B compared to control, d_a and d_b), interactive effect ($DI_{A:B}$, equation 7) with 95% confidence intervals (equation 8), and finally the interaction type characterized, additive (add), synergistic (syn) and antagonistic (ant).

	Parameter	Silver individual Effect Stress	T°C individual Effect Stress	Interaction Effect ($DI_{\Delta T:Ag}$):	Interaction lower CI	Interaction upper CI	Interaction type
AgNP + T°C	Cond	-0.60	10.74	0.38	-1.09	1.86	add
	Oxy	-0.06	-3.66	-0.01	-1.47	1.45	add
	pH	-1.05	0.36	0.03	-1.43	1.48	add
	TC	0.58	-1.05	0.22	-1.24	1.69	add
	TN	0.91	1.34	1.65E-03	-1.46	1.46	add
	TP	0.49	0.70	338.35	143.29	533.42	syn
	Mg	0.28	0.75	-0.07	-1.53	1.39	add
	Ca	0.43	0.84	-1.33	-2.98	0.32	add
	S_nm	0.16	2.39	3113.85	1318.71	4908.99	syn
	Z_mV	-0.02	0.98	1.72	-0.04	3.48	add
	Ag_ion	1.77	bdl	-0.01	-1.46	1.45	add
	Ag_diss	4.98	0.00	4.70	1.62	7.78	syn
	DW	0.33	0.21	176.76	74.85	278.68	syn
	Ag_acc	4.37	-0.70	3620.20	1533.16	5707.25	ant
	Respi	-1.76	1.44	-2.40E-05	-1.46	1.46	add
	Glu_W	0.12	1.34	0.05	-1.41	1.51	add
	Glu_Bio	-1.36	-2.04	0.01	-1.45	1.46	add
	Leu_W	0.09	4.01	-0.41	-1.88	1.07	add
	Leu_Bio	-0.59	-3.58	4.00E-03	-1.45	1.46	add
	Pho_W	0.47	10.28	361.48	153.08	569.88	syn
Pho_Bio	0.33	10.36	-7.92	-12.71	-3.13	ant	
Biomass	0.17	0.21	1022.75	433.13	1612.37	syn	
QYeff	0.35	0.38	9295.43	3936.62	14654.25	syn	
EPS	3.24	2.71	-0.01	-1.47	1.45	add	
	Response variable	Individual Effect Stress Silver	Individual Effect Stress T°C	Interaction Effect ($DI_{\Delta T:Ag2S}$)	Interaction upper CI	Interaction lower CI	Interaction type
Ag₂SNP + T°C	Cond	-1.51	10.74	0.99	-0.57	2.56	add
	Oxy	-0.43	-3.66	0.06	-1.40	1.51	add
	pH	-1.70	0.36	0.06	-1.40	1.52	add
	TC	0.22	-1.05	0.02	-1.43	1.48	add
	TN	-0.07	1.34	1.17E-04	-1.46	1.46	add
	TP	-0.33	0.70	-1433.67	-2260.18	-607.16	syn
	Mg	-0.13	0.75	0.07	-1.39	1.52	add
	Ca	-0.09	0.84	1.66	-0.09	3.40	add
	S_nm	0.41	2.39	-9758.00	-15383.49	-4132.51	ant
	Z_mV	0.01	0.98	1.62	-0.11	3.35	add
	Ag_ion	bdl	bdl	bdl	-1.46	1.46	add
	Ag_diss	bdl	bdl	bdl	-1.46	1.46	add
	DW	0.19	0.21	245.62	104.01	387.23	syn
	Ag_acc	1.56	-0.70	16.52	6.89	26.16	ant
	Respi	0.05	1.44	-7.31E-06	-1.46	1.46	add
Glu_W	0.45	1.34	-2.62	-4.72	-0.52	ant	
Glu_Bio	-1.21	-2.04	2.00E-03	-1.46	1.46	add	

	Leu_W	-1.09	4.01	0.48	-1.00	1.96	add
	Leu_Bio	0.01	-3.58	-0.01	-1.46	1.45	add
	Pho_W	-0.09	10.28	-535.04	-843.50	-226.59	syn
	Pho_Bio	0.57	10.36	3.49	1.01	5.97	syn
	Biomass	-0.02	0.21	1198.12	507.40	1888.83	ant
	QYeff	0.23	0.38	8379.31	3548.64	13209.99	syn
	EPS	1.55	2.71	-0.01	-1.47	1.45	add
	Response variable	Individual Effect Stress Silver	Individual Effect Stress T°C	Interaction Effect ($DI_{AT:AgNO_3}$)	Interaction upper CI	Interaction lower CI	Interaction type
AgNO ₃ + T°C	Cond	-0.49	10.74	-0.56	-2.05	0.94	add
	Oxy	-0.55	-3.66	0.01	-1.45	1.47	add
	pH	-1.58	0.36	0.04	-1.42	1.50	add
	TC	0.35	-1.05	0.05	-1.41	1.51	add
	TN	0.54	1.34	1.45E-04	-1.46	1.46	add
	TP	1.51	0.70	-1094.20	-1725.00	-463.39	ant
	Mg	-0.10	0.75	-0.02	-1.48	1.44	add
	Ca	-0.04	0.84	-0.79	-2.32	0.74	add
	S_nm	0.31	2.39	-2813.99	-4436.26	-1191.73	ant
	Z_mV	0.24	0.98	3.60	1.06	6.13	syn
	Ag_ion	1.28	bdl	-2.00E-03	-1.46	1.46	add
	Ag_diss	1.28	0.00	-0.84	-2.37	0.70	add
	DW	0.00	0.21	25.85	10.88	40.82	syn
	Ag_acc	1.94	-0.70	11.35	4.65	18.06	ant
	Respi	-0.37	1.44	0.00	-1.46	1.46	add
	Glu_W	-0.08	1.34	-0.71	-2.22	0.81	add
	Glu_Bio	-1.80	-2.04	0.01	-1.45	1.46	add
	Leu_W	-0.20	4.01	-0.45	-1.93	1.03	add
	Leu_Bio	-0.40	-3.58	-0.02	-1.48	1.43	add
	Pho_W	0.09	10.28	-525.31	-828.15	-222.47	ant
Pho_Bio	-0.32	10.36	-17.36	-27.47	-7.25	syn	
Biomass	-0.49	0.21	62.12	26.28	97.96	ant	
QYeff	-0.23	0.38	-1073.32	-1692.08	-454.55	syn	
EPS	0.57	2.71	-0.01	-1.47	1.45	add	